

Pattern Recognition Receptors mini review

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Abstract

Pathogen-associated molecular patterns, or PAMPs, are molecules associated with groups of pathogens that are recognized by cells of the innate immune system. These molecules can be referred to as small molecular motifs conserved within a class of microbes. They are recognized by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) which divided into Membrane-bound PRRs (which include Toll-like receptors (TLRs), Receptor kinases, and the mannose receptor), Cytoplasmic PRRs (which include NOD-like receptors, RIG-like receptors, and RNA Helicases, Plant PRRs and NonRD kinases) and Secreted PRRs in both plants and animals. They activate innate immune responses, protecting the host from infection, by identifying some conserved non-self-molecules. Toll like receptor mediate immune response through recognition of pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs), thus play important roles in host defense. The mannose receptor (MR) is a PRR primarily present on the surface of macrophages and dendritic cells. The MR belongs to the multilectin receptor protein group and, like the TLRs, provides a link between innate and adaptive immunity. It recognizes and binds to repeated mannose units on the surfaces of infectious agents and its activation triggers endocytosis and phagocytosis of the microbe via the complement system. The NOD-like receptors (NLRs) are cytoplasmic proteins that regulate inflammatory and apoptotic responses. Approximately 20 of these proteins have been found in the mammalian genome and include two major subfamilies called NODs and NALPs, the MHC Class II transactivator (CIITA), IPAF, BIRC1, and other molecules. NODs are currently known for NOD1 and NOD2. NOD1 recognizes a molecule called meso-DAP, which is a peptidoglycan constituent only of Gram negative bacteria. NOD2 proteins recognize intracellular MDP (muramyl dipeptide), which is a peptidoglycan constituent of both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. NODs transduce signals in the pathway of NF- κ B and MAP kinases via the serine-threonine kinase called RIP2. NALPs are like NODs, these proteins contain C-terminal LRRs, which appear to act as a regulatory domain and may be involved in the recognition of microbial pathogens. Also like NODs, these proteins also contain a nucleotide binding site (NBS) for nucleoside triphosphates. Interaction with other proteins (e.g. the adaptor molecule ASC) is mediated via N-terminal pyrin (PYD) domain. In this Review, we discuss how distinct PRRs (with particular emphasis on TLRs and RLRs) sense the presence of pathogens and cellular insults and the mechanisms by which these PRR signals elicit TLRs and Their Ligands.

Keywords: PRR- TLRs- Bird- Immune response- Innate immunity

Review

The innate immune system is the major contributor to acute inflammation induced by microbial infection or tissue damage (Akira, Uematsu et al. 2006, Beutler, Jiang

et al. 2006). Furthermore, innate immunity is also important for the activation of acquired immunity. Although innate immune cells including macrophages and dendritic cells (DCs) play important roles,

nonprofessional cells such as epithelial cells, endothelial cells, and fibroblasts also contribute to innate immunity. Germline-encoded pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) are responsible for sensing the presence of microorganisms. They do this by recognizing structures conserved among microbial species, which are called pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). Recent evidence indicates that PRRs are also responsible for recognizing endogenous molecules released from damaged cells, termed damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). Currently, four different classes of PRR families have been identified. These families include transmembrane proteins such as the Toll-like receptors (TLRs) and C-type lectin receptors (CLRs), as well as cytoplasmic proteins such as the Retinoic acid-inducible gene (RIG)-I-like receptors (RLRs) and NOD-like receptors (NLRs). These PRRs are expressed not only in macrophages and DCs but also in various nonprofessional immune cells. With the exception of some NLRs, the sensing of PAMPs or DAMPs by PRRs upregulates the transcription of genes involved in inflammatory responses. These genes encode proinflammatory cytokines, type I interferons (IFNs), chemokines and antimicrobial proteins, proteins involved in the modulation of PRR signaling, and many uncharacterized proteins. The expression patterns of the inducible genes differ among activated PRRs.

The inflammatory response is orchestrated by proinflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF), interleukin (IL)-1, and IL-6. These cytokines are pleiotropic proteins that regulate the cell death of inflammatory tissues, modify vascular endothelial permeability, recruit blood cells to inflamed tissues, and induce the production of acute-phase proteins. Although TNF and IL-6 are mainly regulated at the transcriptional and

translational levels, the production of IL-1 β is regulated by a two-step mechanism. The first step is the expression of an IL-1 β zymogen, pro-IL-1 β , which is regulated by the synthesis of its mRNA in a TLR signal-dependent manner. However, IL-1 β maturation requires cleavage of pro-IL-1 β by a protease, caspase-1, which is activated independently of TLR signaling. The complex that activates caspase-1, called the inflammasome, is composed of NLRs, ASC, and caspase-1. Type I IFNs, including multiple forms of IFN- α and single forms of IFN- β , IFN- ω , etc., are also involved in the modulation of inflammation (Honda, Takaoka et al. 2006). Type I IFNs play central roles in antiviral responses by inducing apoptotic cell death in virally infected cells, rendering cells resistant to virus infection, activating acquired immunity, and stimulating hematopoietic stem cell turnover and proliferation. Secreted type I IFNs alert the surrounding cells via type I IFN receptors by triggering a signaling cascade that leads to the phosphorylation and nuclear translocation of IFN-stimulated gene factor 3 (ISGF3), a complex composed of Signal Transducers and Activators of Transcription 1 (STAT1), STAT2, and IFN-regulatory factor (IRF) 9. ISGF3 induces expression of IFN-inducible antiviral genes such as protein kinase R (PKR) and 2' 5' -oligoadenylate synthase (OAS) among others. PKR suppresses the proliferation of virus-infected cells and 2' 5' -OAS activates RNase L, which cleaves viral nucleotides in order to inhibit virus replication.

In this Review, we discuss how distinct PRRs (with particular emphasis on TLRs and RLRs) sense the presence of pathogens and cellular insults and the mechanisms by which these PRR signals elicit inflammasomes and their ligands. The TLR family is one of the best-characterized PRR families and is responsible for sensing

invading pathogens outside of the cell and in intracellular endosomes and lysosomes (Akira et al., 2006). TLRs are characterized by N-terminal leucine-rich repeats (LRRs) and a transmembrane region followed by a cytoplasmic Toll/IL-1R homology (TIR)

domain. Ten TLRs have been identified in humans and 12 in mice. Different TLRs recognize the different molecular patterns of microorganisms and self-components (Table-1).

Table-1 PRRs and Their Ligands

PRRs	Localization	Ligand	Origin of the Ligand
TLR			
TLR1	Plasma membrane	Triacyl lipoprotein	Bacteria
TLR2	Plasma membrane	Lipoprotein	Bacteria, viruses, parasites, self
TLR3	Endolysosome	dsRNA	Virus
TLR4	Plasma membrane	LPS	Bacteria, viruses, self
TLR5	Plasma membrane	Flagellin	Bacteria
TLR6	Plasma membrane	Diacyl lipoprotein	Bacteria, viruses
TLR7 (human TLR8)	Endolysosome	ssRNA	Virus, bacteria, self
TLR9	Endolysosome	CpG-DNA	Virus, bacteria, protozoa, self
TLR10	Endolysosome	Unknown	Unknown
TLR11	Plasma membrane	Profilin-like molecule	Protozoa
RLR			
RIG-I	Cytoplasm	Short dsRNA, 5'triphosphate dsRNA	RNA viruses, DNA virus
MDA5	Cytoplasm	Long dsRNA	RNA viruses (Picornaviridae)
LGP2	Cytoplasm	Unknown	RNA viruses
NLR			
NOD1	Cytoplasm	iE-DAP	Bacteria
NOD2	Cytoplasm	MDP	Bacteria
CLR			
Dectin-1	Plasma membrane	β -Glucan	Fungi
Dectin-2	Plasma membrane	β -Glucan	Fungi
MINCLE	Plasma membrane	SAP130	Self, fungi

TLR2 senses various components from bacteria, mycoplasma, fungi, and viruses. These components include the lipoproteins of bacteria and mycoplasma. TLR2 recognizes its ligands by forming a heterodimer with either TLR1 or TLR6 (Figure 1). The resulting TLR1/TLR2 and TLR6/TLR2 complexes recognize distinct ligands (triacyl and diacyl lipoproteins, respectively). The crystal structures of the extracellular domains of TLR2, TLR1, and TLR6 revealed that they form M-shaped structures and that their cognate ligands interact with internal pockets formed by the TLR1/TLR2 or TLR6/TLR2 heterodimers (Jin et al., 2007). Stimulation with TLR2

ligands, such as triacyl and diacyl lipoproteins, induces the production of various proinflammatory cytokines (but not type I IFNs) in macrophages and DCs. However, another report showed that TLR2 in inflammatory monocytes induced type I IFNs in response to viral infection, suggesting that the cellular responses to TLR2 ligands differ depending on the cell types involved (Barbalat et al., 2009). TLR10 is related to TLR1 and TLR6 based on sequence similarity. TLR10 seems to be functional in humans, although mouse TLR10 is disrupted by insertion of an endogenous retrovirus. The ligand for TLR10 has not been identified.

The pathway of TLR shown in Figure 1, where TLR2, TLR3, and TLR4 Signaling Pathways Lipoproteins and LPS are recognized on the cell surface by a heterodimer of TLR1/6 and TLR2, and by 2 sets of TLR4/MD2 complexes, respectively. Ligand stimulation recruits MyD88 and TIRAP to the TLR, and a complex of IRAKs and TRAF6 is subsequently formed. TRAF6 acts as an E3 ubiquitin ligase and catalyzes formation of a K63-linked polyubiquitin chain on TRAF6 itself and generation of an unconjugated polyubiquitin chain with an E2 ubiquitin ligase complex of Ubc13 and Uev1A. Ubiquitination activates a complex of TAK1, TAB1, and TAB2/3 resulting in the phosphorylation of NEMO and the activation of an IKK complex. Phosphorylated I κ B is degraded, and the freed NF- κ B translocates to the nucleus

where it drives expression of cytokine genes. Simultaneously, TAK1 activates MAP kinase cascades leading to the activation of AP-1, which is also critical for the induction of cytokine genes. LPS induces translocation of TLR4 to the endosome together with TRAM. TLR3 is present in the endosome and recognizes dsRNA. TLR3 and TLR4 activate TRIF-dependent signaling, which activates NF- κ B and IRF3 resulting in the induction of proinflammatory cytokine genes and type I IFNs. TRAF6 and RIP1 activate NF- κ B, whereas TRAF3 is responsible for phosphorylation of IRF3 by TBK1/IKK-i. NAP1 and SINTBAD are required for the activation of TBK1/IKK-i. Phosphorylated IRF3 translocates into the nucleus to induce expression of type I IFN genes.

Figure 1: TLR pathways

TLR4 recognizes lipopolysaccharide (LPS) together with myeloid differentiation factor 2 (MD2) on the cell surface. LPS is a component derived from the outer

membrane of Gram-negative bacteria and is known to be a cause of septic shock. The crystal structure of a complex comprising TLR4, MD2, and LPS revealed that two

complexes of TLR4-MD2-LPS interact symmetrically to form a TLR4 homodimer (Park, Song et al. 2009, Elfeil, Abouelmaatti et al. 2012). TLR4 is also involved in the recognition of viruses by binding to viral envelope proteins. In addition, TLR4 modulates the pathogenesis of H5N1 avian influenza virus infection by recognizing a DAMP rather than the virus itself (Imai, Kuba et al. 2008). Acute lung injury caused by avian influenza virus infection produces endogenous oxidized phospholipids, which stimulate TLR4. Mice lacking TLR4 were found to be resistant to avian flu-induced lethality.

TLR5 is highly expressed by DCs of the lamina propria (LPDCs) in the small intestine, where it recognizes flagellin from flagellated bacteria. In response to flagellin, LPDCs induce B cells to differentiate into IgA-producing plasma cells and trigger the differentiation of naive T cells into antigen-specific Th17 and Th1 cells (Yarovinsky, Zhang et al. 2005, Uematsu, Fujimoto et al. 2008). TLR11, which is present in mice but not in humans, shows close homology to TLR5; TLR11 recognizes uropathogenic bacteria and a profilin-like molecule derived from the intracellular protozoan *Toxoplasma gondii* (Yarovinsky, Zhang et al. 2005).

A set of TLRs, comprising TLR3, TLR7, TLR8, and TLR9, recognize nucleic acids derived from viruses and bacteria, as well as endogenous nucleic acids in pathogenic contexts (Akira, Uematsu et al. 2006). Activation of these TLRs leads to the production of type I IFNs in addition to proinflammatory cytokines. TLR3 detects viral double-stranded (ds) RNA in the endolysosome. TLR3 is involved in the recognition of polyinosinic polycytidylic acid (poly I:C), a synthetic dsRNA analog. Although inoculation of mice with poly I:C induces the production of cytokines as well as type I IFNs in mice, TLR3 is essential for the production of cytokines such as IL-

12p40, but not type I IFNs in sera (Kato, Takeuchi et al. 2006). The crystal structure of TLR3 bound to dsRNA revealed that dsRNA binds to the N-terminal and C-terminal portions of TLR3 LRRs, and this ligand binding dimerizes two TLR3 molecules (Liu, Botos et al. 2008, Choi, Wang et al. 2009). Mouse TLR7 and human TLR7/8 recognize single-stranded (ss) RNAs from RNA viruses, as well as small purine analog compounds (imidazoquinolines). TLR7 also detects RNAs from bacteria such as Group B *Streptococcus* in endolysosomes in conventional DCs (cDCs) (Mancuso, Gambuzza et al. 2009). TLR9 senses unmethylated DNA with CpG motifs derived from bacteria and viruses. Although the CpG motif was thought to be essential for TLR9 stimulation, the DNA sugar backbone of 2' deoxyribose also mediates TLR9 recognition (Haas, Metzger et al. 2008). In addition to DNA, TLR9 also recognizes hemozoin, a crystalline metabolite of hemoglobin produced by the malaria parasite (Coban, Ishii et al. 2005). TLR9 directly binds to hemozoin, and a crude extract of the malaria parasite elicits parasite-antigen-specific immune responses via TLR9 (Coban, Igari et al. 2010). However, another report shows that TLR9 recognizes malaria parasite DNA contained in purified hemozoin, and that hemozoin only transports malaria parasite DNA to the endosome, where TLR9 is present (Parroche, Lauw et al. 2007). Further studies will clarify the role of TLR9 in the recognition of malaria parasite components. TLR7 and TLR9, but not TLR3, are highly expressed in plasmacytoid DCs (pDCs), a cell type that produces large amounts of type I IFNs in response to virus infection.

Accumulating evidence underscores the importance of the localization of TLRs in the cell for their recognition by ligand (Barton and Kagan 2009). Given that self-

nucleotides are potent TLR ligands and may facilitate autoimmunity, TLRs that recognize self-nucleotides are compartmentalized to avoid unwanted activation. Although TLR1, TLR2, TLR4, TLR5, and TLR6 are present on the plasma membrane, TLR3, TLR7, and TLR9 are mainly present on the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) membrane. It has been proposed that self-nucleic acids are degraded by extracellular or endosomal DNases prior to recognition by TLRs. Nucleic acid-sensing TLRs are recruited from the ER to endolysosomes following stimulation by their ligands (Figure 2). The mechanism by which nucleotide-recognizing TLRs are recruited from the ER to the endolysosome compartment remains to be clarified. However, a forward genetics screen in mice revealed that UNC93B1 (an ER protein with 12 membrane-spanning domains) is responsible for TLR3, TLR7, and TLR9 signaling by governing the translocation of these TLRs from the ER to the endolysosome (Tabeta, Hoebe et al. 2006, Kim, Brinkmann et al. 2008). When TLR9 is recruited from the ER to the endolysosome, it undergoes processing by proteases, such as cathepsins, in the endolysosome (Ewald, Lee et al. 2008, Park, Brinkmann et al. 2008). The processed form of TLR9 is responsible for CpG-DNA recognition. It has been shown that cathepsins B, K, and L and asparagine endopeptidase are required for TLR9 responses (Asagiri, Hirai et al. 2008, Matsumoto, Saitoh et al. 2008, Sepulveda, Maschalidi et al. 2009). Currently, it remains unclear whether TLR7 is also cleaved in the endolysosome, although endosomal acidification is required for the sensing of TLR7 ligands.

The intracytoplasmic TLR pathways shown in Figure 2. Nucleic Acid Sensing by TLR7 and TLR9. TLR7 and TLR9 recognize viral ssRNA and CpG DNA, respectively.

Stimulation with ligands or infection by viruses induces trafficking of TLR7 and TLR9 from the ER to the endolysosome via UNC93B1. TLR9 undergoes cleavage by proteases present in the endolysosome. A complex of MyD88, IRAK-4, TRAF6, TRAF3, IRAK-1, IKK- α , and IRF7 is recruited to the TLR. Phosphorylated IRF7 translocates into the nucleus and upregulates the expression of type I IFN genes. Viruses that have entered the cytoplasm are engulfed by autophagosomes and deliver viral nucleic acids to the endolysosome. An HMGB1-DNA complex released from damaged cells is captured by RAGE. Autoantibodies recognizing self-DNA or -RNA bind to Fc γ RIIIa. LL37, an antimicrobial peptide, associates with endogenous DNA. These proteins are responsible for the delivery of endogenous nucleic acids to endolysosomes where they are recognized by TLR7 or TLR9.

TLR7 and TLR9 are essential for virus-induced type I IFN production by pDCs (Kato et al., 2005). Viral nucleotides can interact with TLR7 and TLR9 in pDCs after they have been endocytosed. Alternatively, once the viruses invade pDCs and virions are present in the cytoplasm, they can be delivered to the endolysosome where TLR7 and TLR9 are recruited for viral sensing. pDCs take advantage of a cellular process called autophagy in which self-proteins and damaged organelles are degraded in double-membraned vesicles called autophagosomes (Lee, Lund et al. 2007). In the absence of ATG5, a protein essential for autophagosome formation, pDCs fail to produce type I IFNs in response to virus infection, suggesting that the cytoplasmic virions are engulfed by autophagosomes and then fuse with lysosomes. However, ATG5 is also required for responses to CpG-DNA. Therefore, autophagy may control either the endosomal maturation required for CpG-

DNA sensing or the TLR9 signaling pathways in pDCs, or both.

Figure 2: Nucleic Acid Sensing by TLR7 and TLR9

TLR-mediated microbial recognition is very important for host defense against pathogens. On the other hand, excess responses to TLR ligands induce lethal septic shock syndrome. These observations indicate that appropriate activation of TLRs is vital for eradicating invading pathogens without causing harmful damage to the host.

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